

Like Robots, Like Humans: Pupil Dilation during Collaborative Object Manipulation

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Abstract—It is well known that pupil dilation reflects an increase in cognitive load during tasks that demand mental effort. Inspired by this, we questioned whether the same effect occurs during social interactions, particularly in joint object manipulation tasks that require attention and coordination for successful completion. In the first scenario, we measure pupil dilation during human-human interactive actions (handover), either as the object giver or receiver, against an individual action (pick-and-place). In the second scenario, pupillometry is associated with human-to-robot handovers. We present the two publicly available datasets collected in these contexts.

Our results show a strong link between pupil dilation and collaborative actions, with both humans and robots. Indeed, an increment in pupil size corresponds to the object handover, which presents the added complexity of mutual coordination. Conversely, individual actions do not elicit the same physiological response at the level of the pupil. In both scenarios, we used objects with different physical properties, cups with varying water levels, but this factor influenced pupil dilation (and presumably, the mental workload) only during the interaction with the robot. With this study, we explore pupillometry as a physiological metric to evaluate cognitive load for collaborative object manipulation during human-human or human-robot collaborations.

I. INTRODUCTION

In psychology and neurology, pupillometry describes the act of measuring pupil diameter. It is commonly described in the literature how the pupil constricts in response to brightness and close fixation, while it dilates in reaction to increasing cognitive activity or arousal (this is commonly referred to as psycho-sensory pupil response or task-evoked pupil response) [1]–[4]. This last phenomenon has been investigated mainly from the perspective of mental tasks [5]. Indeed, the pupil reacts to the cognitive load required, for example, by mental calculations [6] or mental rotations [7]. The dilation amount often correlates with the degree of difficulty of the task, and it is also modulated by the level of expertise [8].

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Studying pupil response to physical tasks, especially in a not constrained and realistic environment, is instead more challenging. Inevitable head and body movements cause noise and possible missing data if the gaze exits the field of the eye-tracking cameras. This combines with all the possible influences of acting on the external world: for instance, changing the distance of the fixation point alters the size of the pupil. For these reasons, the effect of demanding motor tasks on pupil diameter still needs investigation. Jiang et al. [9] proposed a visual-motor aiming task where participants had to move a surgical tool to meet targets of different sizes. They found that pupil size increases with task complexity, validating it as an indicator for measuring task workload. However, an important distinction needs to be made between task complexity and precision: while the first increases pupil diameter, the second contracts it, and if both the drives are present, the interpretation of the data may be ambiguous [10]. Regarding autonomous assembly tasks in unconstrained environments, some recent studies reported no conclusive difference in pupil dilation depending on task complexity [11], while others succeeded [12].

As a tool to estimate the workload, either mental or physical, pupillometry can prove useful also to quantitatively assess the interaction with technology. For instance, by providing a way to access the human cognitive state, it could be used to adapt the information exchange with intelligent systems, as needed by human-machine systems for driving assistance [13]. Pupil response was studied in Human-Computer Interaction and findings confirmed that challenging tasks demand longer processing and evoke a significant response at the pupil level [14]. However, in the virtual object manipulation task requiring dragging and dropping emails in the appropriate folder, the same - broad - pupil expansion was observed regardless of the difficulty level. In Human-Robot Interaction (HRI), pupillometry has been used to prove an inversely proportional link between trust and cognitive load [15] and even to detect human lies during an interactive game [16].

A typical daily activity that presents countless variations is object manipulation: depending on the context, the goal, the items involved, and the eventual collaborators in the task, it requires different skills and adaptations. Hence, evaluating how such activity impacts our mental workload is relevant, and a way to obtain this information is through pupillometry. However, as pointed out in the literature overview, there are a limited number of studies that investigate how dilation in the pupil is linked to physical motor activities, especially during

Fig. 1: **Human-Human Interaction** collected with Pupil-Labs glasses from the point of view of a participant. Starting from left to right: grasp the full cup for individual pick-and-place; initiate handover of the full cup; receive the empty cup.

the interaction with robots.

We aim to investigate how the mental effort (perception, cognition, and action) in manipulation tasks (handover or pick-and-place) of plastic cups affects pupil dimension. We already mentioned how an increase in the mental effort of the person reflects in an increment in pupil size. In this sense, we hypothesize (*H1:*) observing pupil dilation in conjunction with the handover, which is a challenging phase in a dyadic collaboration, requiring coordination in time and space between two agents. By using cups with different fillings, empty or containing water, we also address the possible effect of such object property on the pupil’s physiological signal. Hence, (*H2:*) we envisage an increment in pupil size when manipulating cups with water, assuming their handling can be more demanding. Indeed, objects’ filling has been shown to elicit a strong modulation in human kinematics when the cup has water compared to when it is empty, evoking what could be shortly described as careful motion [17]. Moreover, we will present two different interactive scenarios: Human-Human Interaction (HHI), where a pair perform handovers and pick-and-place actions, and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI), where the participant assumes the active role of the giver in the handover, while the robot’s task is to receive the cup. By comparing the two scenarios, we intend to examine whether the physiological response is comparable and thus whether measuring the pupil in HRI could be an useful metric to evaluate task workload when collaborating with robots. Hence, this work gives preliminary insights into the potential use of pupillometry to evaluate human cognitive effort in physical tasks involving objects.

II. HUMAN-HUMAN EXPERIMENT

This section illustrates the HHI setup involving handovers and pick-and-place actions with cups with variable fillings. It includes the scenario description, details of the data publicly available, and the pre-processing techniques adopted to prepare the data for analysis.

A. Scenario

The experiment involves pairs of participants seated at a table in front of each other and tasked with manipulating plastic cups. Each participant has three cups with three levels of water inside: empty, half-full, and 90% full, which we will

refer to as full cup. During the experiment, each participant has to perform a set of actions: picking and placing a cup at a predefined location on the table, passing a cup to the other participant, or receiving a cup from the partner and putting it down (see Figure 1 for an overview). These actions are carried out seamlessly, based on instructions that participants discover one at a time. Because of this, it could happen that when about to receive the cup from the partner, the participant was accomplishing other actions, such as revealing a new instruction or carrying another cup; this contributed to the realism of the task and added an element of potential surprise. For more details on the scenario, please refer to [18].

B. Dataset

Pupil-Labs head-mounted eye-tracker is worn by both participants to track the gaze fixations, pupil dilation, and point-of-view perspective. OptiTrack motion capture markers on the Pupil-Labs glasses and right wrist provide 3D position and orientation of head and hand movements. The data of the eye-tracker and motion capture was recorded at 120 Hz¹. Another typology of ocular data, gaze fixations, collected in the same dataset was already used to classify the water level in cups during handovers in human-human interactions [18]. After providing written informed consent, 6 participants aged 22 to 30 years old, right-handed, five females and one male, all recruited from outside the university, and all naive to the purpose of the research, took part in the experiment in couples of two. A total of 209 cup manipulations are performed: (i) 105 trials for pick-and-place (PP), (ii) 52 trials for the giver in handovers, and (iii) 52 trials for the receiver in handovers. The number of empty, half, and full cups handovers is 17, 19, and 16, respectively. During the pick-and-place and handover actions, participants mostly fixate the cup, their hand, the other’s hand, or face, as stated in [18]. In collecting the dataset, we used artificial light sources while the window blinds were closed throughout to prevent possible physiological fluctuations in pupil size due to light variation.

Fig. 2: **Human-Robot Interaction** scenario. From left to right, the action from the point of view of the participant wearing the Pupil-Labs: pick an empty cup for handover; transport a full cup; the moment of handover of an empty cup. The fixation point is represented by the green dot.

¹The HHI *pick-and-place* and *handover* actions dataset with labels, video, gaze fixations from Pupil eye tracker, head and wrist movements from OptiTrack motion capture is available to on the institution’s https://vislab.isr.tecnico.ulisboa.pt/datasets_and_resources/#hcups_water

C. Data Preprocessing

Pupil signal is a challenging data to treat. Even though current eye-tracking devices, such as the Pupil-Labs, make it possible to obtain measurements using non-invasive methods [19], pupil diameter is noisy and affected by environmental conditions and physiological phenomena. For instance, it must be cleaned from all the blinking, which typically occurs 9 to 13 times a minute [20]. We considered as data source the 3D pupil diameter, measured in mm, provided by the eye-tracker software, which minimizes detection noise and compensates for eyeball distortions [21]. Such a model is initialized during the calibration², performed at the beginning of the experiment, and then updated to compensate for headset slippage and adjustment errors. While pre-processing our dataset, we followed the guidelines by Mathôt et al. [22]. We preliminary removed the data where the eye-tracker software reported a confidence index below 0.6, those missing, and those where the size of the pupil was below 2mm, since the typical range of pupil diameter ranges between 2 and 8mm [23]. We then used cubic-spline interpolation to resample the data in equal intervals of 0.02 seconds, smoothing distorting artifacts. Finally, baseline correction is required to consider random fluctuations in pupil size over time and compare the measured dilation with respect to a reference value. As suggested by Mathôt et al. [22], we opted for subtractive baseline correction by calculating the median value on the subset of data identified as a baseline and subtracting it from the considered trial. We also removed those normalized samples with values which deviated more than 3 times the median absolute deviation. The methodology for selecting the baseline and trial segments will be described specifically in the following section. For each action, we preserved the data from the right or the left eye, depending on which one had more available samples in the trial.

D. Actions description and selection

In the HHI scenario, three possible sets of actions were performed by each participant: autonomous pick-and-place, handover as the giver, or handover as the receiver.

- **Handover as the Giver:** in this case, we consider the point of view of the participant initiating the handover. The baseline comprehends the interval between the beginning and the picking of the cup, while the trial is considered between the picking and the handover moment. Net of trials that we had to discard because of missing or corrupted data (either in the baseline or in action), the available trials are 13 for the full cup, 12 for the half-full, and 16 for the empty one.
- **Handover as the Receiver:** the participant receives the cup from the partner and places it on the table. Since the receiver may be occupied with their tasks (e.g., building their puzzle or moving the cups), the handover may interrupt them. The baseline goes from the trial's beginning to the partner's picking action, while the pupil

is analyzed from the handover moment until the cup is put down. We retrieved 14 trials for each of the 3 cups.

- **Pick-and-Place (PP):** picking up the cup from the table and placing it on a different marked position. We consider as baseline the interval from the trial beginning to the grasp of the cup, and we observe the pupil between the pick and the place. We considered 14 for full cups, and 13 for half-full and empty ones.

III. HUMAN-ROBOT EXPERIMENT

The section presents the second experiment involving a Human-Robot dyadic interaction. It includes the scenario description and an overview of the publicly available dataset.

A. Scenario

In this scenario, participants stand in front of a table where a Kinova gen3 robot with a Robotiq 85 two-finger end-effector is placed. Participants assume the active role of givers in the handover and pick, one at a time, four plastic cups placed in front of them and hand them over to the robot. The cups can either be empty or full of water (90% filled, just like in the previous experiment). The robot receives the cup from the human, pours the water into a bucket if there is water inside, then places the empty or emptied cup inside a drawer on its right. Figure 2 shows the setup, with the robot receiving the cup, an orange bucket meant to contain water, and a blue drawer on the right to store the empty (or emptied) cups. Participants interacted with the robot in two consecutive sessions, whose order was randomly chosen, and which differed for the robot motor control adopted during object transportation towards the containers. This study merges the two conditions since they did not affect the human grasp or handover phases, as they occurred after the human release of the cup. Each volunteer performed 24 handovers of cups, split into sessions of four, in a randomized sequence of empty and full cups. The robot gripper closed for the handover according to a threshold on its distance to the human wrist, tracked throughout the interaction using the OptiTrak motion capture.

B. Dataset

As before, we use Pupil-Labs glasses to gather the eye data. OptiTrack motion capture markers on the eye-tracker, right shoulder, and wrist provide 3D position and orientation of the head, arm, and hand. Additionally, data from an external camera and an IMU sensor on the right wrist are included in the dataset but are not in the scope of this work. For more details, the synchronized and labeled dataset is available at the university website³. The data of the eye-tracker and motion capture was recorded at 120 Hz. Of the 15 participants who took part in the experiment, after providing written informed consent, we consider in this study pupil data acquired from 13 of them (8 females and 5 males, 26.5 ± 6.9 years old), due to problems in the eye-tracker data stream.

²Details on the Pupil Capture Software and calibration can be found at <https://docs.pupil-labs.com/core/software/pupil-capture/>

³The human-to-robot *handover* actions dataset with video, synchronized eye-tracker, motion capture, and inertial data is available on the institution's https://vislab.isr.tecnico.ulisboa.pt/datasets_and_resources/#HRcup

The participants were recruited from all over the campus. Each participant handed over 24 cups, for a total of 312 successful handovers, 156 with empty and 156 with full cups. During the human-to-robot handovers, from videos' visual inspection, participants mostly fixate on either the cup or the robot's gripper. To limit the impact of environmental light's variation on pupil size, the curtains were closed during the acquisitions to filter natural light, and artificial lights from above were used.

C. Actions description and selection

The pre-processing of pupil diameter acquired in the HRI experiment is the same as presented in Section II-C. In the HRI scenario, participants perform handovers as the givers, passing the cups for the robot to grasp. We chose as the baseline a 1-second time interval between the trial's beginning and before the cup picking. The pupil diameter was analyzed between the picking and the handover with the robot. In this case, 120 clean trials were available for full cups and 112 for empty ones.

IV. RESULTS

In this section, given the exploratory nature of this study, are presented some preliminary analyses, such as the temporal evolution of the pupil diameter for the actions of both scenarios. Moreover, we computed the percentage increment of the maximum pupil size during the action with respect to the baseline value.

A. HHI

To obtain a uniform temporal representation of the pupil size, we resampled the available signals to the same length to qualitatively observe their evolution between the start and the end of the action. Then, we proceeded with a baseline correction by subtracting the baseline median value and computing for each sample the mean and standard deviation. Figure 3 shows the corresponding representation for each of the three actions in the HHI dataset. The baseline portion is shadowed in light yellow, while the salient phases of the action (pick, handover, and place) are highlighted with vertical lines marking their occurrences, again with mean value and standard deviation. Referring to Figure 3c, for all three cup types, we do not observe any dilation during the pick-and-place execution. This result appears reasonable given the characteristics of the action, which is ordinary, planned in its whole development by the single participant, and not involving any interaction, hence probably not causing a sufficient mental load to evoke a pupillary response. A different case is represented instead by the handovers, either actively initiated (Figure 3b) or terminated (Figure 3a). When the participant initiates the handover, although the action is known and planned, it involves interacting dynamically with another human with a collaborative intent. We can appreciate in Figure 3b a general dilation of the pupil corresponding to the handover moment. However, the cup's filling seems not eliciting a difference in pupil diameter. As for the case when the participant receives a cup from the

Fig. 3: **HHI** - Dynamics of the pupil size: the pupil size evolution for each of the three cups liquid levels for the Handover as the Receiver (3a), Handover as the Giver (3b), and Pick-and-Place (3c) actions. The colored solid line indicates the mean of the pupil corrected for the baseline and the transparent area, in the same color, its standard deviation. The baseline phase is highlighted in yellow. The grey lines show the moment of picking the cup (dashed), handover (solid line), and placing the cup (end of the sequence). The grey areas represent the standard deviation.

partner, it has already been shown that simply observing human-like motion produces attention and arousal increase that reflects in the pupil size [24]. The actions which involve receiving a cup from another participant present an additional challenge. In this scenario, the person is concentrated on their task and is eventually interrupted to receive one of the three cups. Figure 3a confirms a dilation for all three cup handovers. Additionally, if we consider the interval between the handover and the cup's release, i.e., when the person has the cup in their hand, pupil dilation is prolonged if the cup contains water. At the same time, it rapidly returns to the baseline values for the empty cup. This result could suggest that in situations where the action is not planned beforehand, and the object received has some challenging properties (e.g., the risk of spilling the content), this causes a cognitive load that reflects in the pupillometry, i.e. pupil dilation. Such findings align well with previous studies, since pupillary dilations in response to cognitive processes are small and

Fig. 4: **HHI** - Pupil maximum percentage dilation: maximum value of the pupil dimension with respect to the baseline. The pupil data interval is the active phase of the object manipulations: from pick to handover in the Handover as the Giver, from handover to place in the Handover as the Receiver, from pick to place in the Pick-and-Place task. The colored boxes represent the 25th and 75th percentiles, the colored horizontal line the median. The single data points and the kernel probability density of the data are also reported. The * indicates a significant difference in pupil dilation between the tasks.

Fig. 5: **HRI** - Handover as the Giver: temporal evolution of the baseline corrected pupil size (5a). Figure (5b) shows the maximum pupil dilation with respect to the baseline considering the interval between the picking of the cup and the handover to the robot. The graphical conventions are the same as Figure 3 and 4 respectively.

often around 0.5mm [5], [12]. To support these preliminary insights and gain a more quantitative understanding of pupil dilation associated with different manipulation tasks of cups with variable filling, in Figure 4 we represented the maximum percentage dilation measured in the phase of interest (see Section II-D for reference), with respect to the baseline. This measure was obtained for each trial by dividing the peak of the pupil, corrected to the baseline, for the baseline median value. This representation allows appreciating the magnitude of the dilation in the different actions. We used Jamovi GAMLj module⁴ to run a mixed model assuming the maximum percentage dilation as the dependent variable, the task type, the cup content and their interaction as factors, and the subjects as cluster variables. The pupil percentage increase during the Handover as the Receiver phase resulted significantly higher

than the other two tasks (Receiver – Giver: $estimate = 4.13\%$, $SE = 1.05$, $t = 3.93$, $p < .001$; Receiver – PP: $estimate = 6.55\%$, $SE = 1.07$, $t = 6.12$, $p < .001$). A post-hoc test with Bonferroni correction confirmed these findings (Receiver – Giver: $t(108) = 3.92\%$; Receiver – PP: $t(108) = 6.09\%$ with $p < .001$ for both comparisons). This aligns well with the temporal data represented in Figure 3. The mixed model also reported a difference in pupil percentage dilation between the Handover as the Giver and the Pick-and-Place tasks (Giver – PP: $estimate = 2.41\%$, $SE = 1.05$, $t = 2.29$, $p = 0.02$), but this result was not confirmed by the Bonferroni correction ($t(106) = 2.29\%$, $p = 0.07$). On the other hand, the filling level of the cup had no impact on the percentage increase of the pupil; this result is worth further investigation, expanding the number of participants and trials. We also tested whether the percentage increment in the pupil diameter was significantly above zero, hence proving a meaningful dilation with respect to the

⁴General analyses for linear models Jamovi module: <https://gamlj.github.io/>

baseline phase. We used One-Sample Wilcoxon test after mediating the trials belonging to the same subjects to ensure independence of the samples. We confirmed that the PP task does not affect pupil size, since the test rejected the null hypothesis of the median of the percentage increment being higher than 0 ($HP : \mu_{PP} > 0$, $p = 0.08$, effect size $r = .43$); both the handover receiver (effect size $r = 1$) and the handover giver ($r = .90$) tasks presented instead a significant percentage increase ($p < .001$). It can be observed that the greatest increase (median value of 9%) occurs when receiving a full cup: probably the most challenging scenario evokes a strong pupillary response.

B. HRI

An analogous analysis has been carried out to assess the HRI scenario. In detail, Figure 5a presents the dynamic of the pupillometry during the collaborative action. In this context, participants always acted as the givers in the handover, and the cups' content was either empty or full of water. Interestingly, it can be noticed how the peak in pupil size is reached right before the handover with the robot: this is the most critical part of the interaction due to the risk of dropping the object. After the handover, when the cup is no longer in the participants' hands, and the burden of completing the task falls on the robot, the pupil diameter rapidly decreases. Figure 5b illustrates the maximum percentage dilation considering the interval between the cup picking and the handover with the robot. After averaging the trials of each participant, we used again the One-Sample Wilcoxon test to verify the hypothesis that the median of the distribution is higher than 0, confirming a significant percentage increase of the pupil ($HP : \mu_{pupil} > 0$) for the handover with full cups ($p < .001$, effect size $r = .81$), not for the empty ones even though with a small effect size ($p = .32$, effect size $r = .05$).

Additionally, to compare the dilation measured when handling full or empty cups, we ran a mixed model assuming the maximum percentage dilation as the dependent variable, the cup content as factors, and the subjects as cluster variables. Results show that when passing a full cup to the robot, pupil dilation is significantly higher (Full – Empty: $estimate = 4.57\%$, $SE = 0.74$, $t = 6.18$, $p < .001$). Differently from the findings of the HHI scenario, where the filling level had no impact on the evoked pupillary responses, in this case the pupil dilated significantly only when the handover involved a full cup, with a median percentage increase of 4%, as shown in Figure 5b.

Until now, pupillometry has been used in robotics to study emotions display [25], trust [15], or lie detection [16]. In our study, we offer a preliminary perspective on how pupil physiological responses are associated with joint motor actions with robots and a comparison with physical tasks in dyadic human-human interaction.

V. CONCLUSION

The pupil dilation phenomenon, beyond physiological reaction to brightness and depth of field, has been studied for

a long time as a psycho-sensory response to what, in general, activates the mind [1]–[4], [8]. However, pupillometry has been investigated in a more limited manner for what regards physical motor tasks [10]–[12], [14], with varying results. In this exploratory study, we addressed this last topic as being linked to object manipulation, either autonomous, collaborative with humans or robots. Dealing with real motor actions, pupillometry is particularly challenging and the two presented datasets can be a first step toward studying the mental workload associated with physical tasks.

We found proof of our first hypothesis ($H1$): joint tasks, either with humans (see Figure 4) or robots (Figure 5b), elicit a significant pupil dilation in correspondence with the most critical phase of the action: the handover. Conversely, the same dilation is not detected when participants move objects by themselves, that is, in a pick-and-place action. The second hypothesis ($H2$), assuming that the cups' filling would modulate pupil size, has been matched partially, only during the robot's interaction. In this case, a significant pupil response when passing the full cup, suggests an increased mental workload that can be associated with the risk of spilling the water in the robot's proximity. This could be ascribed to the perceived difficulty of collaborating with an artificial agent for such a complex task. In the HHI dynamics of pupil size in Figure 3, we still observed a sustained dilation for the cups containing water, after the handover until the placing of the cup; conversely, a rapid decrease in the pupil size occurs after the handover for the empty cup. The more sustained increase in mental effort, given in this case by the water inside the cup, could cause a prolonged dilation at the eye level, as suggested by [1].

This preliminary study aimed to show how pupil physiological responses can represent a useful quantitative metric for evaluating task workload, also as a comparison between human-human and human-robot physical interaction. In the future, we devise the need to conduct more extensive studies with a larger number of participants to explore these insights and challenging research questions further, extending the pool of objects and tasks considered.

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